

**“TO STUDY THE EFFECT OF INCLUSIVE ENVIRONMENT ON
DIFFERENTLY ABLED CHILDREN” – A LITERATURE REVIEW**

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Abstract

Universalization of Education provided an opportunity for the children to access education free of cost and study myriads of subjects in the mainstream, but the Universalization of education also brought challenges in educating children who are having different abilities. Children who are differently abled in learning, intellectual, emotional and psychological faces barriers in learning and satisfying educational needs because of the restrictive environment in the mainstream schools. The findings and results of researches provide an insight of a least restrictive environment where children with and without disabilities can learn, share, collaborate, and cooperate together in the same environment, such a conducive environment is called as an Inclusive Education. Thus, this study provides a review of selected literature found in the area of Inclusive Education, Special Education and Children with different abilities. This study will be helpful towards getting literature available on Inclusive Environment, Special Education and Children with different abilities domain at a glance for different purposes.

Keywords: *Inclusive Education, Special Education, Differently Abled Children,*

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At the beginning of the 21st century Special education solved most of the problems faced by children with different abilities, but from research it was found that these children are vulnerable to sociological and psychological problems because of the restrictive environment provided in the special schools, thus a school with the least restrictive environment for the differently abled students, should be provided to differently abled students. In special education children with severe disabilities were provided with a restrictive environment where children with disabilities get neglected with the benefits of having social environment and relationships with their peer groups who are without any severe disabilities (JUDY WILLIS, 2007). In order to provide a conducive and least restrictive environment to the children with and without disabilities, a mainstream school should include all the children with different abilities in a single educational setup, in such an Inclusive Environment, children with and without disabilities learn, share, collaborate, and cooperate together in the same environment. According to (Thousand, 2005), Inclusive education is defined as

“Embracing children with and without disabilities and making a commitment to provide each child in the society, each citizen in a democracy, with the inalienable right to belong. In an inclusive environment learning and satisfying needs of education benefits not only children without abilities and with abilities equally”.

Objectives of the study

To identify literature published on Inclusive Environment and Differently Abled Children.

To discover the literature published on the effect of Inclusive Environment on differently abled children.

To analyze literature published on the effect of Inclusive Environment on differently abled children.

Methods used in the study

In this study, to identify and discover the literature published on the effect of Inclusive Environment on differently abled children, the researcher used search engines, databases, directories and combination of words to search the literature. Following the combination of words were used to search literature; “Inclusive Environment”, “Learning Outcomes”, “Children with and Without Disabilities”, and “Special Education”. Following are the Search Engines, Directories and Data Base were used to search literature, “Google”, “Google Scholar”, “Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ)”.

Literature Review

In their study (Abeywickrama, Jayasinghe, & Sumanasena, 2013), examined children with different abilities, their parents, and teachers in three special education schools of Sri Lanka. (Abeywickrama et al., 2013), Investigate experiences of Children with different abilities, Families, and Teachers in Sri Lanka. In this study, the researcher used qualitative self-employed participatory tools and in-depth interviews to find the influence of physical, social and psychological environments on participation in learning of children with different abilities. (Abeywickrama et al., 2013), used a sample 20 children with different abilities, 18 parents and 8 teachers for the study, the results obtained in this research focuses on attitudes, beliefs values, the support provided by the environment and relationships. Besides this technology, supportive devices and services used in the environment were affecting the learning of children with different abilities, in this study identification of barriers and facilitating of learning among children with different abilities were studied. Further, it was found that support and extracurricular activities were found to enhance learning among

children with different abilities. Based on the findings (Abeywickrama et al., 2013), concluded that though inclusive environment facilitates learning among children with different abilities there should be a paradigm shift in the practices in education for children with disabilities. As observed by (Abeywickrama et al., 2013), in the developing country the main barrier to the inclusive environment is the services and resources provided to the inclusive school by the stakeholders. A locally compatible model with low-level setting should be designed for an inclusive environment, keeping in view the values, beliefs, attitude towards children with different abilities. Strength of the children with disabilities should be recognized and positive expectations from the children should be made so as to encourage children with different abilities in learning and restrict wastage and stagnation of these children.

Findings by, (Preeti & Kiran, 2012), revealed that institutions belonging to the non-government were providing more infrastructure, services, and facilities for children with different abilities as compared to the institutions belonging to the government. Findings of the study show that 74.28% of the students belonging to Institutions run by Government had a low level of satisfaction as compared to 55.71% of students belonging to non-Government institutions. Thus findings suggest that conducive, suitable and barrier-free inclusive environment in institutions helps in providing convenience and satisfy the educational needs of the children with different abilities.

In their study, (Zwane & Malale, 2018), provides information with regard to barriers in the implementation of inclusive education and finding its solutions for making policies and implementation. In this study, Researchers used the qualitative method, participant observation, and Interview to find barriers in the implementation of inclusive education in the schools. In this investigation the researcher used Non probability, purposive sampling, (Zwane & Malale, 2018), used 14 teachers from a population of 60 teachers from which 7 participants from School A and 7 from School B. The findings show some barriers in government schools where there is lack of infrastructure and facilities, further the teachers are incompetent in identifying children with different abilities and the challenges these children are facing in the inclusive environment. In their research, (Zwane & Malale, 2018), concludes that the government should frame policies and inclusive curriculum based on the needs of children with different abilities. In order to enhance capacities and competencies, a pre-service teacher training program should be conducted in order to bring a positive effect to the competencies

of the teachers. Barriers in implementing successful inclusive school can be removed by redesign the curriculum to satisfy learning needs for children with different abilities and diverse learning needs.

In their study on children with different abilities, (Holt, Bowlby, & Lea, 2019), investigates the differences in schooling, educational needs and the disability among children with different abilities and the influence of their class and capitals. In this study (Holt et al., 2019), used qualitative and participants' observation method to find the effect of class and capital on children with different abilities. In this study, semi-structured interviews with 64 educational persons with a total of 40 professional and 24 parents were selected as a sample, (Holt et al., 2019), suggested that the inequalities and differences among children with different abilities (physical, mental and emotional), are underexplored. These inequalities and differences in class and capital do not allow children with different abilities to reach their full potentials.

(García-Carrión, Roldán, & Campos, 2018), investigates the enhancement of quality of education of children with different abilities in special schools. In this study, the researcher suggests that if interactive learning environments can be developed and provide better opportunities and support to children with different abilities. Designing Interactive Learning Environments for the Educational needs of children with different abilities in Special Schools. A case study was conducted with 36 students from the age group 6 to 14 years old with different abilities and teaching staff in a special school. Research findings by (García-Carrión et al., 2018), suggests that learning, behavior, and classroom interactions can be enhanced among the children with different abilities by transforming and reorganizing the available resources and facilities. Further, in this study, the reorganization and transformation of resources bring complex challenges and limitations in constructing a better inclusive environment. Thus improvement in the quality of education can be achieved by creating an interactive learning environment in the inclusive settings thus removing barriers of social exclusions.

Conclusion

A review of the literature using search engines, database and directories were used to identify and discover the effect of inclusive environment on differently abled children. An analysis of literature provides insights on suggests that inclusive environment is beneficial to children with and without disabilities, as observed by (Abeywickrama et al., 2013), inclusive

environment facilitates learning among children with different abilities and there should be a paradigm shift in the practices and methods used in the institutions catering the educational needs of the differently abled children. A study by (Zwane & Malale, 2018), provided an overview regarding removing barriers in education and diverse learning needs of differently abled children by redesigning the curriculum.(García-Carrión et al., 2018), suggests that learning, behavior, and classroom interactions can be enhanced among the children with different abilities by transforming and reorganizing the available resources and facilities.

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